

INCREASING THE EFFICIENCY OF SOLAR PHOTOELECTRIC STATIONS USING SOLAR MOVEMENT OBSERVATION EQUIPMENT

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Abstract: Development and improvement of the efficiency of the solar movement tracking mechanism for photovoltaic batteries. The proposed two-axis solar monitoring device is used in low-power solar photovoltaic stations and can also be used in other types of solar energy installations.

Keywords: photovoltaic battery, actuator, hydraulic drive, lever.

Аннотация: Разработка и повышение эффективности механизма слежения за движением солнца для фотоэлектрических батарей. Предлагаемая двухосная солнечная наблюдательная установка используется в маломощных солнечных фотоэлектрических станциях и может быть использована в других типах солнечных энергетических установок.

Ключевые слова: Фотоэлектрическая батарея, актуатор, гидропривод, рычаг.

Annotatsiya: Fotoelektrik batareyalar uchun quyosh harakatiga nisbatan kuzatuv mexanizmini ishlab chiqish va samaradorligini oshirish. Taklif etilayotgan ikki o'qli quyosh kuzatish uskunasi kam quvvatli Quyosh fotoelektirik stansiyalarda qo'llaniladi va boshqa turdagi quyosh energetik qurilmalarida ham qo'llash mumkin.

Kalit so'zlar: Fotoelektrik batareya, aktyuator, gedroyuritma, rechak.

Solar monitoring equipment plays a crucial role in the efficiency of solar photovoltaic stations. These devices are used to direct solar panels or modules at the most efficient angle to sunlight. By tracking the movement of the sun, these devices constantly adjust the solar panels to the best light, which allows them to accumulate more solar energy and convert it into electrical energy. Solar photovoltaic plants are environmentally friendly, safe, and cost-effective.

Solar photovoltaics (SPP) has been growing in the global market by an average of 40% annually since 2005. Over the next 20 years, more than 2 million jobs are expected to be created thanks to solar photovoltaics. As a result, 350 million tons of CO₂ emissions into the atmosphere will be reduced, and 140 coal-fired power plants will be shut down. The total capacity of solar photovoltaics will reach 650 GW by 2030. Solar energy, as a natural and limitless source, is becoming increasingly important in the modern world. In countries like Uzbekistan, which are characterized by a large number of sunny days, solar photovoltaic stations (SPS) create enormous opportunities for the economy and the environment. However, the efficiency of these stations often depends on the intensity of sunlight and the angle.

Two-axis solar monitoring devices ensure maximum sunlight reception by tracking the sun's movement and directing solar photovoltaic panels directly towards the sun. These instruments move along the azimuth and zenith axes, so they can accurately track the movement of the sun across the sky during the day.

To increase the efficiency of solar photovoltaic panels, biaxial solar monitoring devices have the following advantages:

By constantly directing the panels towards the sun, solar photovoltaic panels receive more solar radiation and thus generate maximum electrical energy.

The best aspect of the two-axis solar monitoring equipment is that they move along the azimuth and zenith axis along the solar trajectory throughout the day and ensure that sunlight falls perpendicularly on the surface of solar photovoltaic panels.

The initial investment costs required for the solar monitoring equipment can pay off in the short term.

Changes in solar radiation values during the day

Dynamics of changes in the maximum power of solar photovoltaic installations during the day

Dependence of AB voltage on discharge time

As can be seen from the graph above, in winter, under semi-clear weather conditions, the average daily power of solar PVS with and without a solar observation device differed by 25%.

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